

(Correlation Between Entry-Route and Age on Academic Performance in ... Shodeinde, A. O. & Obikoya, T. S. 2025)

**Correlation between entry-route and age on academic performance in
Electrical/Electronic Technology Education programs among undergraduate students
in Southwest, Nigeria**

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Abstract

This study investigated the correlation between entry-route and age on academic performance in electrical/electronic technology education programs among undergraduate students in Southwest, Nigeria. The study was guided by two research questions. A correlational research design was adopted, and data were collected from 92 students using a structured questionnaire (ERAQ) and official academic records. The instrument was face-validated by three experts. Reliability test of the instrument was done using a test-retest method, and a coefficient of 0.88 was obtained. Descriptive statistics were used to summarize demographic information, while point-biserial correlation was employed to examine the relationships among variables. Findings revealed that 58% of the students' gained admission through the O' Level route, while 42% entered with OND, NCE, or other post-secondary qualifications. Additionally, the majority (63%) were aged 20 years and below. Results showed a positive and statistically significant relationship between academic performance and both entry route ($r = .841, p < .01$) and age at enrolment ($r = .879, p < .01$). Specifically, students who entered with OND, NCE, and other post-secondary qualifications, as well as those above 20 years of age, performed better academically than their counterparts. The study concludes that prior academic experience and student maturity contribute positively to academic achievement in technical education. Based on the findings, it was recommended that educational policymakers consider differentiated academic support for students based on their entry route and age, and that universities provide targeted interventions to enhance performance, particularly for younger students and those admitted via the O' Level route.

Keyword: Entry-route, Age, Academic performance

(Correlation Between Entry-Route and Age on Academic Performance in ... Shodeinde, A. O. & Obikoya, T. S. 2025)

Introduction

Academic performance is an important indicator of student success and institutional effectiveness in higher education. According to Oriakhi and Ujiro (2015), academic performance refers to the degree to which a student, teacher, or educational institution has successfully met their learning objectives or educational targets. In technical education programs such as Electrical/Electronic Technology Education, student performance is not only a reflection of individual capabilities but also a measure of how well the educational system prepares students for the demands of a technologically driven world. According to Haj (2020), students' academic performance is influenced by several factors, including the route through which students gain university admission and their age at enrolment.

Entry route refers to the qualification pathway through which students are admitted into university such as O' Level, OND (Ordinary National Diploma), NCE (Nigeria Certificate in Education), and other post-secondary credentials. In the context of Nigerian universities, such as University of Nigeria, Tai Solarin University of Education, among others, candidates admitted to these tertiary institutions to study technical education programs such as Electrical/Electronic Technology Education must have attained certain minimum requirements such as; Five O/level credits, including English Language and either Physics or Mathematics, obtained in no more than two sittings from examinations such as WASC, SSCE, GCE (O/L), NECO, or NABTEB. Additionally, City and Guilds intermediate qualification plus a credit in Mathematics or Physics from WASC, SSCE, GCE (O/L), NABTEB, National Technical Certificate, or WASC Technical Certificate are acceptable. For Direct Entry (DE) admission, candidates must have at least a National Diploma (ND) in Engineering fields such as Civil, Mechanical/Production, Electrical/Electronics, or Building/Wood, or have achieved Distinction, Credit, or Merit in NCE (Technical). According to Richardson, Abraham and Bond (1998) in Rosalba et al (2021), universities often base their students' admission on entry-route or pre-university academic performance because they believe it will influence the students' academic success during their time at the institution.

While some students are admitted through the traditional O' Level qualifications obtained in senior secondary school, others enter with post-secondary qualifications such as the Ordinary National Diploma (OND), Nigeria Certificate in Education (NCE), or other equivalent credentials. Apart from those admitted through O'Level, students who gain admission through other pathways would have gotten foundational academic and vocational training before they pursue university degrees. Due to this, there is an assumption that students with prior post-secondary education will possess more refined study skills, greater academic maturity, and practical exposure that may give them a performance advantage at the university level. In support of this view, Adeyemi (2010) and

(Correlation Between Entry-Route and Age on Academic Performance in ... Shodeinde, A. O. & Obikoya, T. S. 2025)

Adebayo and Ojetunde (2012) indicated that students with OND or NCE backgrounds often outperform their counterparts who gained admission through O' Level due to better subject mastery and practical experience. However, not all scholars agree on the superiority of post-secondary entry routes. Oladejo (2015) argued that entry route alone does not significantly predict academic performance; instead, factors such as study habits, motivation, and quality of instruction may play a more substantial role.

In addition to entry route, age at enrolment is another variable linked to academic performance. Even though, age is discussed as a potential determinant of academic performance, different scholars have taken conflicting position on it. According to John, Jackson and Simiyu, (2015), the chronological age of a students had a significant bearing on his/her academic performance such that the younger ones had the potential of having higher score than his/her older counterpart in teacher made tests. They further noted that as age increases, working memory declines and this affects learning because it can make tasks, such as, problem-solving and decision-making more difficult. Furthermore, Omolayo and Idowu (2017) found that younger students, particularly those recently graduated from secondary school, often perform better in academic tasks due to their mental agility, familiarity with structured learning environments, and lack of competing responsibilities such as work or family. In contrast, Chinyoka and Naidu (2014) observed that older students generally exhibit higher levels of academic discipline and motivation, which often translate into better performance. Jegede (2016) also reported similar findings among distance education students in Nigeria, where older learners demonstrated superior academic outcomes attributed to greater self-directedness and goal clarity.

Despite these conflicting perspectives, what remains clear is that age at enrolment interacts with academic performance. Investigating the interaction between entry route and age at enrolment is relevant in the context of technical education in Nigeria, where diverse educational backgrounds and wide age ranges are common among university entrants. Moreover, while previous studies have investigated the influence of age and entry route on academic performance in general education contexts, there is a dearth of research focused specifically on technical education programs such as Electrical/Electronic Technology Education. Therefore, the rationale for this study lies in the need to fill this knowledge gap by investigating how entry route and age at enrolment relate to the academic performance of Electrical/Electronic Technology Education students in South-West Nigeria. Findings from this study can inform university admission strategies, curriculum planning, and support services aimed at enhancing student performance in technical education programs.

(Correlation Between Entry-Route and Age on Academic Performance in ... Shodeinde, A. O. & Obikoya, T. S. 2025)

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of the study was to examine the correlation between entry-route and age on academic performance in electrical/electronic technology education programs among undergraduate students in Southwest, Nigeria. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. Find out the relationship between entry routes (O' Level, diploma, etc.) and the academic performance (GPA) of electrical/electronic technology education students in South-West, Nigeria.
2. Examine how age at enrollment correlate with the academic performance (GPA) of electrical/electronic technology education students in South-West, Nigeria.
- 3.

Research Questions

1. What is the relationship between entry routes (O' Level, diploma, etc.) and the academic performance (GPA) of electrical/electronic technology education students in South-West, Nigeria?
2. How does age at enrollment correlate with the academic performance (GPA) of electrical/electronic technology education students in South-West, Nigeria?

Methodology

Research Design: Correlation research design was used for the study. According to Gay, Mills & Airasian (2011), correlation survey research design established the relationship among variable such that the it could determine the how one or more predictor (independent) variables are related to or predict one or more outcome (dependent) variable. Thus, the researcher deems it fit to use correlation design for this study because it enabled the researcher to collect data from a group of students which was used to represent the entire population and then determine the relationship between the variables of this study namely, entry-route, age, and academic performance.

Population of the Study: The entire population of 300 level electrical/electronic technology education students' universities in Southwest, Nigeria was used for this study. The population comprised of 92 electrical/electronic technology education students.

Sample and sampling technique: This study did not employ any sampling technique. Due to the manageable size of the population, the entire 92 electrical/electronic technology education students participated in the study.

Research Instrument: A self-structured questionnaire titled: Entry Route and Age Questionnaire (ERAQ), which measured Entry-Route and Age of participants was used for data collection in the study. In order to determine students' academic performance, data on the Grade Point Average (GPA) of students were requested from their departments.

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(Correlation Between Entry-Route and Age on Academic Performance in ... Shodeinde, A. O. & Obikoya, T. S. 2025)

Validity of the Instrument: The instrument (ERAQ) which was used for data collection was face-validated by three experts in the Department of Technical Education, Tai Solarin University of Education, Ijebu-ode Ogun State. The suggestions of the experts were incorporated into the final draft of the instrument.

Reliability of the Instrument: Reliability test of the instrument was done using a test-retest method. Copies of the instrument was administered twice on 20 Technical Education students at Delta State University which is not part of the study area within two-week interval and a coefficient of 0.88 was obtained.

Procedure of Data Collection: Data were collected using validated instruments. Introduction letter was presented to the department of each participating university seeking their permission and approval to carry out the study among their students. The researcher’s administered the instrument with the help of four research assistants. Hundred percent (100%) questionnaires retrieval rate was achieved.

Method of Data Analysis: Data collected for the study were analyzed using frequency counts, percentages, and Point-Biserial Correlation (PBC). Decision for the range of R-values are: (a) from 0.01 to 0.20 represent very low/weak correlation, (b) from 0.21 to 0.40 represents low/weak correlation from n, (c) from 0.41 to 0.60 represent moderate/average correlation, (d) from 0.61 to 0.80 represent high/strong correlation, (e) from 0.81 to 0.99 represent very high/strong correlation. Where $r = 0$ or 1 represents no correlation or perfect correlation respectively (Uzoagulu, 2011).

Presentation of Results

Entry Route of the Respondents: The respondents were asked to indicate their entry route into the university, and the responses are shown below.

Table 1: Distribution by Entry Route

Entry Route	Frequency	Percent (%)
O’ Level	53	58
OND, NCE, Other post-secondary qualifications	39	42
Total	92	100

Source: Field Work (2024)

Table 1 shows the distribution of respondents based on their entry route into electrical/electronic education program. Out of a total of 92 respondents, 53 students (representing 58%) gained admission through the O’ Level route, while 39 students (42%)

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entered with OND, NCE, or other post-secondary qualifications. This indicates that the majority of the respondents entered the program directly with O' Level qualifications.

Age of the Respondents: The respondents were also asked to indicate their age group in the administered questionnaire. The respondents' responses are thereby shown in the table below.

Table 2: Distribution by Age

Age	Frequency	Percent (%)
20 years and below	58	63
Above 20 years	34	37
Total	92	100

Source: Field Work (2024)

From Table 2, the distribution of the respondents by age revealed that 58 (63%) are aged 20 years and below, while 34 (37%) are above 20 years. From the analysis, the majority of the respondents are aged 20 years and below.

Academic Performance of Respondents: Information on the academic performance of students were also collected in the study and its distribution is shown in Table 3.

Table 3: Academic Performance

CPGA	Frequency	Percent (%)	Remark
1.01 - 2.39	32	35	Fail
Above 2.40	60	65	Pass
Total	92	100	

Source: Field Work (2024).

Table 3 depicts the academic performance of the respondents in the study based on their Cumulative Grade Point Average (CGPA). Out of 92 students, 32 (35%) have a CGPA between 1.01 and 2.39, which is classified as a fail, while 60 (65%) have a CGPA above 2.40, indicating a pass. Based on the aforementioned, it can be inferred that the majority of the respondents had a good grade in the third year (300Level) and at the time of the study.

Research Question 1

What is the relationship between entry routes (direct admission, diploma, etc.) and the academic performance (GPA) of electrical/electronic technology education students in South-West, Nigeria?

(Correlation Between Entry-Route and Age on Academic Performance in ... Shodeinde, A. O. & Obikoya, T. S. 2025)

Academic Performance (AP) and Entry-route

The first research question was to establish the extent to which entry-routes and academic performance of electrical/electronic technology education students are related. Point Biserial Correlation (PBC) was adopted as a data analysis technique to answer the research question. It is used to measure the strength and direction of the association that exists between one continuous variable and one dichotomous variable. PBC output is shown in Table 4.

Table 4: PBC Outputs for AP and Entry-Route

		Academic Performance	Entry-Route
Academic Performance	Pearson Correlation	1	.841**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	92	92
Entry-Route	Pearson Correlation	.841**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	

Source: SPSS Outputs (Version 26)

A point-biserial correlation as indicated in Table 4, was calculated to find out the relationship between entry routes and the academic performance of electrical/electronic technology education students. The findings revealed that there was a very strong, positive and statistically significant relationship between students’ academic performance and entry route, ([92]) $r = [.841]$, $P = .000$ at a 1% level of significance. Since OND, NCE, and other post-secondary qualifications was coded as 2, the output indicated that students who gained admission through OND, NCE, and other post-secondary qualifications performed better academically than those who entered through the O’ Level route.

Research Question 2

How does age at enrollment correlate with the academic performance (GPA) of electrical/electronic technology education students in South-West, Nigeria?

Academic Performance (AP) and Age

The second research question posed in the study is "How does age at enrollment correlate with the academic performance (GPA) of electrical/electronic technology education students

(Correlation Between Entry-Route and Age on Academic Performance in ... Shodeinde, A. O. & Obikoya, T. S. 2025)

in South-West, Nigeria?” The Point Biserial Correlation (PBC) outputs for the question are shown in Table 5.

Table 5: PBC Outputs for AP and Age

		Academic Performance	Age
Academic Performance	Pearson Correlation	1	.879**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
Age	Pearson Correlation	.879**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: SPSS Outputs (Version 26)

Table 5 contains the point-biserial correlation used to examine the relationship between the academic performance of electrical/electronic technology education students and age at enrolment. The finding indicates that there was a very strong, positive and statistically significant relationship between students’ academic performance and age, ([92]) $r = [.879]$, $P = .000$ at a 1% level of significance, indicating that students above 20 years of age performed better academically than those aged 20 years and below.

Findings of the Study

1. Students who gained admission through OND, NCE, and other post-secondary qualifications performed better academically than those who entered through the O’ Level route.
2. Students above 20 years of age performed better academically than those aged 20 years and below.

Discussion of Findings

The findings of this study provide information into how students’ entry routes and age at enrolment relate to their academic performance in Electrical/Electronic Technology Education programs in South-West Nigeria. First, the analysis of entry routes shows that a larger proportion of students gained admission into the program through the O’ Level route, while the remaining were admitted via OND, NCE, or other post-secondary qualifications. Despite this higher number of O’ Level entrants, the point-biserial correlation analysis revealed a strong and statistically significant positive relationship between entry route and academic performance. Since higher entry codes were assigned to OND, NCE, and similar

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(Correlation Between Entry-Route and Age on Academic Performance in ... Shodeinde, A. O. & Obikoya, T. S. 2025)

qualifications, this result indicates that students who entered the program with post-secondary qualifications outperformed those admitted through the O' Level route. This suggests that the additional academic experience and technical training gained through diploma and certificate programs may better prepare students for success in university-level studies. In line with the findings of the study, Adeyemi (2010) found that students with prior post-secondary qualifications such as OND or NCE performed significantly better in teacher education programs compared to their counterparts admitted through O' Level.

The study attributed this to the advanced preparation and subject familiarity of the diploma entrants. Similarly, Adebayo and Ojetunde (2012) also reported that polytechnic graduates transitioning into university degree programs tend to outperform their peers who entered directly from secondary school. The authors argued that the practical exposure and discipline instilled during diploma programs contributed to better academic outcomes. In the same vein, Okebukola (2014) emphasized the importance of foundational knowledge, asserting that students who enter with technical or professional certificates often possess better problem-solving skills and learning strategies, which enhance their academic performance at the university level. However, the findings of Oladejo (2015) contradicted the findings of this study. He argued that there is no significant difference in academic performance between students admitted through direct entry (OND/NCE) and those with O' Level qualifications. The study noted that performance is more influenced by study habits and institutional support than entry background.

Furthermore, findings on research question two regarding the relationship between students' age at enrollment and academic performance indicates that the majority of students were aged 20 years and below. However, the point-biserial correlation between age and academic performance showed a statistically significant positive relationship, signifying that older students (above 20 years) performed better academically than their younger counterparts. This may be attributed to greater maturity, discipline, or prior academic and life experience among older students, which could positively influence their academic engagement and performance. Previous studies supported the findings of the study. Chinyoka and Naidu (2014) found that older students tend to perform better academically than their younger peers, particularly in technical education programs.

The study attributed this to greater emotional maturity, motivation, and clarity of purpose. Jegede (2016) also reported a significant positive relationship between age and academic performance among distance learners in Nigeria. He noted that older students were more likely to be self-directed, disciplined, and better at time management. In the same vein, Terenzini et al. (1996), concluded that older students often outperform younger students in higher education settings, largely due to life experience and a strong sense of responsibility.

(Correlation Between Entry-Route and Age on Academic Performance in ... Shodeinde, A. O. & Obikoya, T. S. 2025)

However, in contrast to the study findings, Omolayo and Idowu (2017), suggested that younger students tend to perform better in science and engineering courses due to cognitive agility and recent exposure to structured academic environments in secondary schools. Ali et al. (2009) also indicated that while older students may have the advantage of maturity, their performance can be negatively affected by family responsibilities, work commitments, and reduced academic stamina.

The findings suggest that both age and prior academic qualifications are predictors of academic success in Electrical/Electronic Technology Education programs. Students with prior post-secondary experience and those above 20 years of age tend to perform better. This points to the value of maturity and foundational knowledge in achieving better academic outcomes.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of this study, it can be concluded that both the entry route and age at enrolment are factors influencing the academic performance of Electrical/Electronic Technology Education students in South-West Nigeria. Students who gained admission through OND, NCE, and other post-secondary qualifications performed better academically than those who entered directly through the O' Level route. This means that prior academic and technical training provides a strong foundation for success in university programs. Similarly, students above 20 years of age demonstrated higher academic performance compared to their younger counterparts. This suggests that maturity and experience contribute positively to academic performance.

Recommendations

1. Institutions should provide additional academic support, such as foundation courses, for students admitted through the O' Level route.
2. Admission policies should continue to encourage and possibly expand access for candidates with OND, NCE, or other relevant post-secondary qualifications.
3. Universities should establish mentorship programs for younger students to help them develop better study habits, time management, and academic discipline.

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